

Fertilizer management—organic sources

Salinity tolerance of some *Azolla* spp.

J. Majumdar, V. Rajagopal, and M. V. Shantaram, Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry Department, College of Agriculture, Andhra Pradesh Agricultural University, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 500030, India

Soil salinity is a serious problem for rice culture in many coastal areas of southern India. If azolla is to be used in these areas, it must be screened for salinity tolerance.

In a greenhouse study, we tested the salinity tolerance of five *Azolla* spp. by artificially salinizing the soil to 5 and 8 dS/m. Soil (5 kg) in shallow pots (45 cm diam, 20 cm deep) with 10 cm standing water was inoculated with 5 g azolla (fresh weight). The experiment had three replications, with nonsalinized soil as control. The fresh weight of azolla fronds was recorded 30 d after inoculation (see table).

Soil salinity decreased biomass production in all of the species. *A. microphylla* and *A. mexicana* had greater tolerance for salinity than *A. pinnata* and *A. filiculoides*. The study indicates the potential of *A. mexicana* and *A. microphylla* for use as a biofertilizer in saline rice soils. The mechanism for salinity tolerance of the two species needs further study. ■

Effect of salinity on the growth of azolla species.

Azolla species	Azolla (g fresh wt /0.16 m ²) at indicated soil salinity level (dS/m)			
	0.3 (control)	5.0	8.0	Mean ^a
<i>A. caroliniana</i>	51.30	34.34	4.72	30.12
<i>A. pinnata</i>	49.80	35.37	2.77	29.31
<i>A. filiculoides</i>	41.63	21.80	4.70	22.71
<i>A. mexicana</i>	72.10	50.07	18.60	46.72
<i>A. microphylla</i>	81.40	51.53	21.73	51.65
LSD (P = 0.05)				
Azolla species	3.50			
Salinity levels	4.70			

^aMean of 3 treatments

Rock phosphate is an effective P carrier for azolla

J. Majumdar, V. Rajagopal, and M. V. Shantaram, Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry Department, College of Agriculture, Andhra Pradesh (AP) Agricultural University, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 500030, India

P fertilizer is the most critical and costly input for the cultivation of rice and azolla. Most soils used for growing rice in AP are P deficient, which adversely affects the multiplication of azolla. Single superphosphate (SSP) at 8.8 kg P/ha is recommended for growing azolla, but SSP is expensive. We investigated using rock phosphate (RP), which is a less expensive source of P than SSP.

In a greenhouse experiment, we added 4.4, 8.8, and 17 kg P/ha as SSP (16%

water-soluble P₂O₅) and RP (21% total P₂O₅) to a Vertisol that had 8.8 kg native P/ha. Combinations of SSP and RP to supply 4.4 + 4.4, 2.9 + 5.9, and 2.2 + 6.6 kg P/ha were also used.

Fronds of *A. caroliniana* and *A. pinnata* (Rajendranagar strain) were inoculated at 10 g fresh weight/pot (45 cm diam, 20-cm-deep, containing 5 kg soil). Each treatment was replicated three times. The fronds were harvested, blotted on absorbent paper, and weighed to get the fresh weight of azolla 30 d after inoculation (see table).

Azolla responded positively to both P sources. Equal biomass was produced using up to 8.8 kg P/ha as SSP and up to 17 kg P/ha as RP. Of all the combinations of SSP + RP tested, 1:1 was best, which was on par with the two treatments above. RP can be used as a total or partial substitute for SSP, thus reducing the cost of inputs for azolla. ■

Efficiency of single superphosphate and phosphate rock as P source for azolla.

P treatment	Azolla biomass production (g fresh wt/0.16 m ²)		Mean ^a
	<i>A. caroliniana</i>	<i>A. pinnata</i>	
Control	61.8	49.4	51.6
SSP 4.4 kg P/ha	88.7	68.1	78.4
SSP 8.8 kg P/ha	148.1	104.0	126.0
SSP 17 kg P/ha	152.4	111.5	132.0
PR 4.4 kg P/ha	78.5	79.1	78.8
PR 8.8 kg P/ha	97.7	93.1	95.4
PR 17 kg P/ha	120.7	119.1	123.9
SSP ^b + PR 1:1	154.7	100.1	127.4
SSP ^b + PR 1:2	124.7	100.2	112.5
SSP ^b + PR 1:3	86.9	105.9	96.4
Mean	112.2	93.1	
LSD (P = 0.05)			
Azolla species		3.8	
Treatments		8.4	

^aMean of 3 replications. ^bAt 8.8 kg P/ha.

Influences of soybean N fixation on soil N balance in rice - soybean rotation

Ying Ji-feng, China National Rice Research Institute, Hangzhou 310006, China

Soybean has a significant role in maintaining the soil N fertility in rice - soybean cropping systems. We examined the effects of soybean N fixation on N

fertility of the ricefield in a rice - soybean rotation.

The experiment was conducted in a sandy loam San Sai soil with pH 5.7-5.9 and 0.05-0.06% total N from Chiang Mai, Thailand (19° N, 99° E), from Aug 1988 to Apr 1989. Chiang Mai has a definite wet season (WS) and dry season (DS). The nine treatments included a factorial combination of N fertilizer applied to rice